

A DFT study on trapping of nitric oxide by 1,3,2,5-diazadiborinine, a frustrated Lewis pair

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Manuscript received 23 July 2018, accepted 10 August 2018

Nitric oxide (NO) can be trapped by a "frustrated Lewis pair" (FLP) containing two ambiphilic boron centers as shown through the results from a DFT based computation. There are three possible ways in which NO can bind to the FLP. Among the three possible paths only two are thermodynamically favorable with respect to enthalpy as well as free energy changes. However, all the products are kinetically favorable as explained by lower values of free energy barriers (less than 15.0 kcal/mol). The favorable orbital interactions between the HOMO of FLP and LUMO of NO play a crucial role in giving these three possible products as revealed by molecular orbital analysis, which is further confirmed by NBO analysis, where the net gain of electron density is shown to take place on the NO segment. On the other hand, the WBI values along with the AIM analysis reveal that all the newly formed B-N and B-O bonds are partially covalent in nature.

Keywords: Nitric oxide, frustrated Lewis pair, transition state, molecular orbital analysis.

Introduction

One of the simplest radicals, nitric oxide exists in the gas phase at room temperature. It has significant biological functions in cellular signaling and vascular muscle relaxation¹. It acts as a valuable messenger in biological systems². Therefore, the trapping of NO and its limited release have been widely studied³⁻⁵. There are several text book examples of stable nitroso complexes of transition metal atoms^{6,7}. However, there are a few organic molecules that can effectively capture and release NO¹. Recently it has been found that N-heterocyclic carbenes can be considered to be promising candidates in fixing NO^{8,9}. But, the problem is that a higher temperature is necessary for the thermal release of NO⁹.

The concept of "frustrated Lewis pair" (FLP) as proposed by Stephan in 2009 has seen a recent upsurge of interest in chemical reactivity, in which the steric interaction prevents the Lewis acid-base adduct formation and thus they have potential for showing novel reactivity^{10,11}. For instance, there are some FLPs which can split H₂ molecule heterolytically and act as metal free hydrogenation catalyst¹²⁻²⁸. Moreover, FLP can potentially activate a number of small molecules which include CO₂^{29,30}, N₂O³¹⁻³⁴, C₂H₄³⁵, C₂H₂³⁶, etc. Recently, Erker and co-workers reported that capture of NO also becomes possible using FLPs³⁷⁻³⁹. They have also shown

that the capture of NO by a vicinal FLP follows the first order kinetics with respect to NO⁴⁰. Recently Wu and co-workers have synthesized 1,3,2,5-diazadiborinine which contains an aromatic C₂B₂N₂ skeleton⁴¹. They have shown that among the two boron centers of 1,3,2,5-diazadiborinine one is nucleophilic and another is electrophilic in nature and thus the species has an ability of showing an FLP type behavior⁴¹. It has ability of activating CO₂, derivatives of alcohol and alkyne as demonstrated by their results. Later on they have reported that the species may undergo a [4+2] cycloaddition reaction with ethylene and styrene derivatives in a concerted way⁴².

Here, the possibility of NO trapping ability using this species has been investigated by applying a density functional theory based computation. For this purpose, we intend to provide the thermochemical results in terms of free energy (ΔG) and enthalpy (ΔH) changes at room temperature. Next, we analyze the kinetic stability of the desired NO trapped species in terms of free energy barrier. The nature of bonding between the FLP and NO has been understood on the basis of molecular orbital (MO), natural bond orbital (NBO) and atoms-in-molecules (AIM) analyses.

Computational details

All the molecules involved in the work are modeled using

Gauss View 5.0 software⁴³. Geometries of all the species including reactants, transition states (TS) and products of the reactions are optimized at the B3LYP^{44,45} density functional level and 6-31+g(d) basis set is used for all the atoms and no constraints have been applied during geometry optimization. The important geometrical parameters of central B₂C₂N₂ skeleton of 1,3,2,5-diazadiborinine (as only this segment has participated in the reaction) from the optimized geometry are compared with the crystallographic data reported by Wu *et al.*⁴¹ and the two sets of results match satisfactorily (see Table S1 in Supporting Information). So, all the results reported here are computed at B3LYP/6-31+g(d) level. Harmonic vibrational frequencies are calculated in order to ascertain the nature of the obtained stationary points on the related potential energy surfaces. All the reactants and products reported herein comprise only real vibrational frequencies (NIMAG=0) whereas the TS structures contain one imaginary vibrational frequency (NIMAG=1) each. Frequency calculation also provides thermal correction to energy, which in turn gives Gibbs free energy and enthalpy values. In order to connect the transition state (TS) with the desired minima, an

intrinsic reaction coordinate (IRC) calculation has been carried out for all the transition states (TS). All the electronic structure calculations have been carried out with the help of Gaussian 09 software package⁴⁶. The nature of bonding has been understood based on the NBO analysis⁴⁷ which gives the NPA charge on each atomic center and the Wiberg bond index value (WBI) between two atoms⁴⁸. The AIM analysis⁴⁹ is also performed to get a detailed insight into the bonding nature. For this analysis Multiwfn software⁵⁰ has been utilized.

Results and discussion

We first analyze the optimized structures obtained when NO gets attached to the FLP. It appears that NO is trapped by the FLP in three possible ways (Fig. 1). When oxygen site of NO gets attached to the B1 center of the FLP, it gives rise to the product A, when the same is attached to the B2 center of the FLP, it gives rise to the product B and when the nitrogen site of NO gets attached to both the boron centers, product C is formed. The N-O bond distance in the free NO gas molecule was 1.16 Å as calculated at B3LYP/6-31+g(d) level.

Fig. 1. Optimized geometries of the FLP and the three possible products A, B and C when NO is trapped by the FLP, calculated at the B3LYP/6-31+g(d) level. Necessary bond distances are given in Å unit. Color code: black for carbon, blue for nitrogen, red for oxygen, pink for boron, sky blue for hydrogen.

After reaction with the FLP it increases to 1.36 Å (in A), 1.36 Å (in B) and 1.28 Å (in C) respectively.

The NO trapping ability of the FLP is estimated in terms of binding energy (BE), enthalpy (ΔH) and free energy (ΔG) changes involved in the formation of the three isomers (A, B and C) and the calculated values are given in Table 1. Since, the BE values gradually decrease from A to C it implies that the NO trapping ability of the FLP is best for A, followed by B and C. Although, the ΔH values are negative in all the cases showing exothermicity of all the reaction paths, it is shown by the ΔG values that only A and B are formed exergonically under standard conditions (i.e. at 298 K temperature and 1 atm. pressure). The kinetic stability of the products is estimated by calculating the free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) of each of the three reaction paths (see Table 1). It appears from the calculated values of ΔG^\ddagger that, product C should be kinetically more favorable ($\Delta G^\ddagger = 9.0$ kcal/mol) in comparison to the products A and B ($\Delta G^\ddagger = 14.2$ and 13.1 kcal/mol, respectively). But, if one compares the thermodynamic criteria, then it is transparent that the products A and B should be more favorable than product C.

Table 1. ZPE corrected binding energy (BE), enthalpy change (ΔH) and free energy changes (ΔG) at 298.15 K, for NO trapping by the FLP at B3LYP/6-31+g(d) level. All energies are given in kcal/mol

System	BE	ΔH	ΔG	ΔG^\ddagger
A	-15.7	-16.8	-4.9	14.2
B	-11.7	-12.8	-1.0	13.1
C	-0.8	-1.5	8.8	9.0

Bonding analysis:

In order to gain an insight into the formation of these three possible products we analyzed the reaction mechanism in terms of frontier molecular orbital interactions. Fig. 2 displays the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) of the FLP and NO and their respective energy values are given within parentheses. The HOMO and LUMO energy values along with their orbital symmetry clearly indicate that, the HOMO of FLP may interact with the LUMO of NO in two possible ways to give A and B. Here, we can mention that these two products are formed in a concerted [4+2] type cycloaddition reaction. There is also another possibility where the HOMO of FLP interacts only with the nitrogen site of NO using the LUMO to give the product C.

Fig. 2. Selected frontier molecular orbitals (HOMO and LUMO) along with their corresponding energies values (in eV) of the FLP (left) and NO (right).

To get a better understanding about the bonding and stability of the products, an NBO analysis was performed at the same B3LYP/6-31+g(d) level. The NPA charges and WBI values of selected atoms and bonds respectively are given in Table 2. Before binding with NO the NPA charges on B1 and B2 centers were 0.68 au and 0.00 au respectively within the FLP, indicating that B1 center has an ability to accept electron density whereas, B2 center has electron density donating ability. Thus, the boron centers become ambiphilic as suggested by Wu *et al.*⁴¹. After binding of NO to the FLP, the overall charge of the NO segment becomes negative which suggests that the electronic charge density is transferred from the FLP to the NO moiety. This should happen because the HOMO of the FLP is interacting with the LUMO of NO in all cases. Looking at the charge on B1 and B2 centers we observe that the positive charge at the B1 center decreases slightly and it increases at the B2 center. This observation was expected from the electrophilic nature of B1 center and nucleophilic nature of B2 center. The calculated WBI values reveal that almost all of the B-N and B-O bonds exhibit partial covalent character and B-N bonds are

Table 2. The NBO atomic partial charges (in au) and WBI values of some selected atoms and bonds calculated at the B3LYP/6-31+g(d) level

System	q^N	q^O	q^{B1}	q^{B2}	q^{NO}	WBI (N-O)	WBI (B-O/N)
NO	0.20	-0.20	-	-	0.00	2.106	
FLP	-	-	0.68	0.00		-	
A	-0.17	-0.52	0.70	0.09	-0.69	1.152	0.690 (B-O), 0.821 (B-N)
B	-0.25	-0.47	0.53	0.28	-0.72	1.154	0.668 (B-O), 0.864 (B-N)
C	-0.30	-0.41	0.61	0.17	-0.72	1.318	0.757 (B1-N), 0.719 (B2-N)

more covalent than B-O bonds. The WBI value of the N-O bond within free NO gas molecule was 2.106 and after binding with the FLP it reduces to 1.152, 1.154 and 1.318 within the product A, B and C respectively. This suggests that the N-O bond gets activated in all the products and the activation follows the order $A > B > C$. The similar order is also found in the N-O bond length within the products.

We also performed AIM analysis to make a deeper understanding of the bonding characteristic in between the B-O and B-N bonds within A, B and C. Various electron density descriptors (au) calculated at the bond critical points (BCPs) of B-O and B-N bonds within A, B and C are provided in Table 3. Generally, high positive value of electron density ($\rho(r_c)$) and negative value of Laplacian of electron density ($\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$) at a BCP suggest the covalent nature of a chemical bond. But it is found that typical covalent bond like F-F in F_2 molecule gives a positive $\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$ value⁵¹. In those cases the electron energy density ($H(r_c)$) at the BCP provides an additional measure of covalent character of such a bond. Thus, the negative ($H(r_c)$) value at the BCP reveals some sort of covalent character of the bond. From Table 3 we see

Table 3. Electron density descriptors (au) at the bond critical points (BCPs) of newly formed bond between the FLP and NO. Atom numbering is being followed from the images in Fig. 1

System	BCP	$\rho(r_c)$	$\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$	$H(r_c)$
A	B1-O	0.148	0.447	-0.107
	B2-N	0.145	0.154	-0.125
B	B1-N	0.168	0.168	-0.152
	B2-O	0.131	0.380	-0.093
C	B1-N	0.158	0.148	-0.141
	B2-N	0.137	0.106	-0.119

that, although $\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$ is positive at the BCP of all B-N and B-O bonds, the ($H(r_c)$) is negative in all cases showing partial covalent character of all the bonds. The contour line maps of $\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$ are depicted in Fig. 3, where the purple lines correspond to $\nabla^2\rho(r_c) > 0$ and green lines correspond to $\nabla^2\rho(r_c) < 0$. The green region is developed in between all of the B-N and B-O bonds showing the accumulation of electron density in between the concerned bonds, although $\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$ is positive in all cases as the BCP is slightly shifted from the green region. This observation is significant, since the electron densities are transferred from the FLP to the NO segment.

Fig. 3. Plots of Laplacian of electron density ($\nabla^2\rho(r)$) of the products (a) A, (b) B and (c) C at B3LYP/6-31+g(d) level.

Conclusion

NO trapping ability of an intramolecular FLP containing ambiphilic boron centers has been investigated by DFT calculation. Geometry optimization results in three possible ways of trapping of NO to give the products A, B and C. Although, C is kinetically more favorable product in comparison to A and B as the free energy barrier for the formation of C is comparatively small (9.0 kcal/mol) in comparison to that of A and B (14.2 and 13.1 kcal/mol respectively), the thermochemical results demonstrate that only A and B would be formed spontaneously. The formation of these three possible products can be clearly understood from molecular orbital analysis, where the HOMO of the FLP interacts with the LUMO of NO in three possible ways. This was further confirmed by NBO analysis, which shows the net gain in electron density at the NO segment in all the cases. On the other hand, the WBI values along with the AIM results reveal that all the newly formed B-N and B-O bonds are partially covalent in nature.

Acknowledgements

PKC thanks Professor Chittaranjan Sinha for inviting him to contribute this article to this special issue. He would also like to thank DST, New Delhi for the J. C. Bose National Fellowship. MG thanks CSIR, New Delhi for his senior research fellowship.

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